

BOOK of ABSTRACTS

International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing

**1st International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing
10th-11th October 2019
Novi Sad, Serbia**

Title:

Book of Abstracts of the 1st International Conference on Advanced Production and Processing publishes abstracts from the following fields: Innovative Food Science and Bioprocesses, Nutraceuticals and Pharmaceuticals, Sustainable Development, Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Materials Design and Applications, Petroleum Refining and Production.

Publisher:

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

For publisher:

prof. Biljana Pajin, PhD, Dean

Editorial board:

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Editor-in-Chief:

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Design and Printing Layout:

Saša Vulić, Tamara Krstić

CIP - Каталогизacija y publikaciji
Biblioteka Maticе српске, Нови Сад

658.5(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Conference on Advanced Production and Processing (1 ; 2019 ;
Novi Sad)

Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / 1st International Conference on Advanced
Production and Processing, 10th-11th October 2019 Novi Sad ; [editor-in-chief Senka
Vidović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Technology, 2019

Nasl. s naslovnog ekrana.

ISBN 978-86-6253-102-5

a) Технологија - Производња - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 330974471

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REACTION OF INOCULATED CANCERS ON NITRIC OXIDE HYPERPRODUCTION, GLUCOSE ENERGY, FOLATE AND VITAMIN B₁₂ INHIBITION IN YOUNG HAMSTERS

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We investigated the effect of the nitric oxide hyperproduction, glucose energy, folate and vitamin B₁₂ inhibition caused by nitroglycerin and metformin on fibrosarcoma in young hamsters. The 24 Syrian golden hamsters of approximately 40 g, both sexes, were randomly allocated in 3 experimental and 1 control groups of 6 animals in each. 2 x 10⁶ BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously on the back of animals in all groups. The first experimental group started daily peroral treatment with nitroglycerin 50 mg/kg, second with metformin 500mg/kg and third with a combination of nitroglycerin 50 mg/kg and metformin 500 mg/kg, via gastric probe 3 days before tumor inoculation. After 2 weeks, when the tumors were ~2cm in the control group, all animals were sacrificed, blood collected for glucose and other analyses, tumors excised, weighed, diameters measured, tumor samples pathohistologically (HE) and immunohistochemically (Ki-67, CD 31, COX IV, GLUT-1, iNOS) assessed and main organs toxicologically analyzed. Tumor volume was determined using the water displacement method and the formula $L \times S^2 / 2$, L - the longest, S - the shortest diameter. Ki-67-positive cells in tumor samples were quantified. Images were taken and processed by imaging software. Statistical significances were determined by the one way ANOVA. The combination of nitroglycerin and metformin significantly inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in hamsters without toxicity. Administration of nitroglycerin with metformin might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant pediatric anti-cancer treatment.

Keywords: Fibrosarcoma, Young hamsters, Nitroglycerin, Metformin

Acknowledgements: To Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Provincial Secretariat for High Education and Scientific Research [grant no. 142-451-2413/2018 (JP)] and Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Science [grant nos. 171039 (JS) and 172013 (DM)].